

Preparation and Properties of 3-Aryl-5-Arylazo-thiazolidine-2,4-diones

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In contrast to earlier claims, the compounds reported here represent the true azo-derivatives of 3-substituted thiazolidine-2,4-diones. Comparison of spectral data with those of analogous compounds as well as other properties suggest that the derived compounds essentially exist in the azo-form.

Our recent work on azo-rhodanines¹ directed our attention to a report by Bhargava and Sharma² describing the synthesis and the characterisation of 5-arylazothiazolidine-2,4-diones (III) from I. Since a reactive methylene group is involved in both the cases (I and II), azo-coupling should proceed under comparable condition; and the properties of the products, evidently, should be sufficiently close to one another. However, careful repetition of Bhargava's experiments entirely failed to give any product (III, X = Y = H) comparable to azo-rhodanine (IV, X = Y = H). Indeed, the starting material could be isolated in an almost quantitative yield. It appears that the compounds previously claimed to be III are in suspect; a reinvestigation on the titled compounds was therefore initiated. In fact, the authors² failed to quote any physical parameter in support of their compounds; for instance, aryl-azo derivatives are known³ to display intense long wave length absorption bands.

Under the circumstances, a series of azo-derivatives (III) were synthesized from appropriate diones and substituted anilines. As anticipated, the desired compounds (III) could be obtained only under alkaline condition as in the case of rhodanines¹. But the yield is invariably modest and this is understandable in terms of weaker acidity⁴ of the 5-methylene group of I compared to that in II.

The properties of the azo-compounds are summarised in Tables 1 and 2. Evidence in support of their assigned structure (III) are as follows: the dione (I, X = H) shows a

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TABLE 1

Properties of 5-Arylazo-derivatives of 3-arylthiazolidine-2,4-diones.

Sl. No.	Compd. (III) X = H Y =	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Form	Analysis (%)			
					Found C	Found H	Calcd. C	Calcd. H
1	H	194-95	34	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	60.65	3.81	60.61	3.70
2	<i>p</i> -Me	173-74	42	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	61.52	4.22	61.73	4.14
3	<i>p</i> -MeO	156-57	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	58.61	3.99	58.71	3.97
4	<i>p</i> -OH	229-30 dec.	20	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₃ S	57.72	3.33	57.51	3.51
5	<i>p</i> -Cl	204-5	31	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	54.32	2.99	54.29	3.01
6	<i>m</i> -Cl	207	25	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	54.41	3.00	54.29	3.01
7	<i>p</i> -Br	200-1	32	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	48.02	2.36	47.87	2.66
8	<i>p</i> -I	210-11	20	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ IN ₃ O ₂ S	42.38	2.52	42.53	2.36
9	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	259-60 dec.	20	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	52.78	3.01	52.63	2.92
10	<i>p</i> -COOH	286-87 dec.	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ S	56.29	3.35	56.30	3.22
11	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	274 dec.	20	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	48.01	3.21	47.87	3.19
	Y = H X =							
12	<i>p</i> -Me	168-69	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	61.65	3.74	61.73	4.14
13	<i>p</i> -MeO	215-16	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	58.66	3.98	58.71	3.97
14	<i>p</i> -Cl	194-95	23	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	54.08	3.11	54.29	3.01
15	<i>p</i> -Br	206-7	24	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	47.63	2.74	47.87	2.66

strong peak at 225 m μ (ϵ , 7610) with indication of another submerged band around 252 m μ . But the azo-derivatives (III) display a strong and broad band in 240-250 m μ region (which sometimes appear as shoulder) with two other weaker bands around 290 m μ . But the most notable feature of the absorption curve is a highly intense and almost symmetrical band ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) in the 360-390 m μ region with λ_{\max} values comparable to those of azo-rhodanines indicating the occurrence of *trans*-arylazo fragment in III. However, inspection of data in Table 2 suggests that the substituents on the azo-phenyl fragment at C₅ exert appreciable influence on the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ band position, but this is not observed when the substituents are inserted on the phenyl ring at N₃. Nevertheless, absorption pattern remains the same for the whole series, and the gross similarity between the two sets of azo-derivatives (III and IV, X = Y = H) is a clear indication of the nature of the chromophore in III.

Further, IR spectrum of the typical member (III, X = Y = H) is remarkably similar to the corresponding azo-rhodanine (IV, X = Y = H). In the carbonyl region, the former shows two intense bands at 1735 and 1680 cm⁻¹ in contrast to a single band at 1725 cm⁻¹ in the latter. Presumably, the band at 1680 cm⁻¹ could be attributed to carbonyl group

TABLE 2

TLC and spectral data of Azo-thiazolidinediones (III)

Sl. No. of compounds in Table-1	Rf × 100		Colour in Alkali	MeOH	
	Solv. SA	Solv. SB		λ_{max}	$m\mu$ ($\epsilon \times 10^{-3}$)
1	33	32	Dp. Yellow	369(25.86); 296(2.93)*; 285(3.64)*; 245(12.53)sh	
2	38	40	„	376(25.55); 302(3.33)*; 292(3.88)*; 247(12.22)sh	
3	28	27	„	387(25.78); 311(4.82)*; 300(5.03)*; 245(12.58)sh	
4	6.5	4.0	„	392(21.27); 313(4.40)*; 303(4.65)*; 240-2(12.23)sh	
5	31	34	„	370(28.38); 305(4.76)*; 294(4.56)*; 250(13.05)sh	
6	40	39	Orange	362(27.64); 300(4.14)*; 290(4.48)*; 246(15.53)*	
7	32	35	Dp. Yellow	371(30.77); 305(5.34)*; 294(5.13)*; 250(14.32)sh	
8	40	36	„	372(31.78); 307(5.18)*; 298(4.77)*; 250(16.17)*	
9	28	16	Pink	392(46.55)	
10	~0	~0	Orange	371(31.66); 300(3.65)*; 290(5.02)*; 265(11.61)*	
11	~0	4.0	Dp. Yellow	365(31.58); 299(4.70)*; 288(4.97)*; 257(12.72)*	
12	46	36	Orange	368-9(24.62); 297-8(3.63)*; 285-6(4.15)*; 245(14.0)sh; 224(17.88)*	
13	36	32	Dp. Yellow	370(25.23); 297-8(4.27)*; 287(4.97)*; 245sh, 231(24.88)	
14	46	40	„	372(23.41); 297-8(3.49)*; 287(4.07); 226(20.65)*	
15	45	43	„	367(20.89); 297-8(4.18)*; 287(4.87); 232(22.28)*	

(*) broad band, approx. mid-position indicated.

(sh) = shoulder.

at C₂. Besides other arguments in favour of the azo-structure apparently hold good as in the case of azo-rhodanines¹ and arylazo-pyrazolones⁵. Another recent example, comparable to the present situation, is found with diazo-coupling products (V) of ethyl *p*-toluenesulfonyl acetates; here also the authors⁶ assigned azo-structure to their products on the basis of NMR

Fig. 1. Comparison of absorption spectra between III and IV (X = Y = H).

and IR spectra. However, some uncertainties about azo-hydrazo tautomerism in III still persists to the extent that some significant absorption was found to occur around 3190 cm^{-1} .

TLC experiments provided intense yellow spots with R_f values as noted in Table 2. But in some instances there were very faint indications of companion compounds with R_f values twice as much as the main spot. While the electronic absorption pattern of the major spot was identical with the starting material, attempts to identify the other fraction (collected through preparative TLC) were not conclusive. At any event, although the possibility of tautomerism could not be excluded, the azo-form (III) is apparently predominant.

Chemically, the azo-dyes (III) behaved like acid-base indicators as in the case of azo-rhodanines⁷. The light yellow solutions in acid medium usually give rise to different shades of colour in alkaline medium depending on the nature of the *para*-substituent on the azo-phenyl fragment at C_5 . Further, we were unable to cause any fission of the azo-linkage in III ($X = Y = H$) with sodium dithionite in aqueous alcoholic medium as claimed by Bhargava and Sharma². Russian workers had the same experience as ours with arylazo-derivatives of benzimidazole (2',1'-2,3)thiazolidine⁸.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Substituted thiazolidine-2,4-diones were obtained by known method, and m.ps. agreed well with the literature values : 3-phenyl-, $147-48^\circ$, lit.⁹, 148° ; 3-*p*-tolyl-, 163° lit.¹⁰, 163° ; 3-*p*-chlorophenyl-, $141-42^\circ$, lit.¹¹, $136-37^\circ$, 145° ; 3-*p*-bromophenyl-, $162-3^\circ$; lit.¹², 163° ; 3-*p*-anisyl-, $163-4^\circ$, lit.¹³, $160-1^\circ$.

Absorption spectra were recorded in acetone-free methanol (BDH) with Hilger recording spectrophotometer. IR spectra (KBr) were taken with Perkin-Elmer Infracord. TLC experiments were conducted with plates coated ($250\ \mu$) with silica gel G, dried at 120° for 1 hr and were used in the same day. Development solvents were : SA : Chloroform : acetic acid (95 : 3, v/v) ; SB : Benzene : Et acetate (92 : 8, v/v).

Preparation of the diazo-derivatives (III) ; General description : Aniline or substituted anilines (5 m mole), dissolved in 6*N* hydrochloric acid (3.5 ml.), was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.35 g. in minimum volume of water) at ice-bath temperature. The resulting clear solution was gradually added with stirring to a previously well-cooled (0.5°) solution of the dione (5 m mole) in dimethyl-formamide (7.5 ml.) containing triethyl amine (7.5 ml.). Separation of any gummy material was prevented by occasional addition of cold 95%

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alcohol. After complete addition, the mixture was stirred for 15 min. more, acidified with dilute acetic acid and carefully diluted with cold water until crystalline material separated. The precipitated solid was collected, washed with water and crystallised from methanol (charcoal).

In cases where dilution with water resulted in the separation of gummy material, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and the mixture was left overnight under refrigeration. The product was collected and crystallised as before. The yield was 20 to 40% as recorded in Table I. Analytical samples were obtained after two more crystallisations.

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